

Wake up! Little Forest Elves

Ting Chuang Liew, Saito University College [tcliew@saito.edu.my]

This is a collaboration project of AIIZ Printing Sdn. Bhd. and 180 Virtual Introverted Sketchers group (180VIS) funded by AIIZ as a form of sponsorship to 180VIS. This pictorial book cum monthly calendar will be printed in limited quantities. A large portion of the printed material will be given away as gifts to Chinese schools through Jiao Zong. Another half as merchandise to raise funds for 180VIS's following publication – a brief history of local en plein air development and influential group leaders (1950s–2020s).

It took only a fortnight duration for the editorial. I would like to express my gratitude to the editorial team, especially guest editor Ms Tang Pui Kwan, who is willing to join us for this meaningful project.

To embrace the notion of Back to basics in art. 180 Virtual Introverted Sketchers (180VIS) was founded last year in October during the lockdown. It is a 180-minute virtual en plein air session, non-tutorial, a weekly gathering, with pre-recording HD video, then we sketch, draw, and paint together in a Zoom meeting. Conceptually, we depict the projected visual and audio in the virtual platform to capture the "outdoor" phenomenon through the laptop monitor. While we stay safe at home, we can still listen to Mother Nature and sketch in location virtually. On the other hand, it is also a weekly exercise; the practice of silence is power.

We have captured selected scenes/buildings from Kajang, Klang, Bukit Jalil, Puchong, Seremban, Tapah, Johor Bahru, Jenjarum, Teluk Air Tawar, and recently featured Petaling Street. We have organised more than 50 virtual en plein air (still counting) and 2 physical ones.

Our administrator team would like to thank you for presenting this meaningful publication entitled "Wake up! Little Forest Elves"